

AUTONOMY IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: The article devoted to open the theme autonomy in learning foreign languages and covers information about importance of self- study in learning languages. Furthermore, in the article methods and strategies of self development were noted.

Key words: *autonomous learning, learning strategies, selfesteem, Introspective reports, Retrospective self-reports, motivation, confidence.*

Autonomy means the ability to take control of one's own learning, independently or in collaboration with others. An autonomous learner will take more responsibility for learning and is likely to be more effective than a learner who is reliant on the teacher. Learner training in the classroom encourages autonomy and is an important element of language teaching. In the classroom asking learners to keep diaries to reflect on the way they learn best, and teaching them how to use tools such as dictionaries can encourage autonomy. Asking the question, 'could the learners do this for themselves?' about any activity planned for class will help create the conditions for the development of greater learner autonomy in class.

The concern of the present study has so far been with outlining the general characteristics of autonomy. At this juncture, it should be reiterated that autonomy is not an article of faith, a product readymade for use or merely a personal quality or trait. Rather, it should be clarified that autonomous learning is achieved when certain conditions obtain: cognitive and metacognitive strategies the part of the learner, motivation, attitudes, and knowledge about language learning, i.e., a kind of metalanguage. To acknowledge, however, that learners have to follow certain paths to attain autonomy is tantamount to asserting that there has to be a teacher on whom it will be incumbent to show the way. In other words, autonomous learning is by no means «teacherless learning.» As Sheerin succinctly puts it, 'teachers-have a crucial role to play in launching learners into self-access and in lending them a regular helping hand to stay afloat[1].

Probably, giving students a «helping hand» may put paid to learner autonomy, and this is mainly because teachers are ill prepared or reluctant to 'wean [students]-away from teacher dependence'. After all, 'it is not easy for teachers to change their role from purveyor of information to counsellor and manager of learning resources. And it is not easy for teachers to let

learners solve problems for themselves'[2]. Such a transition from teacher control to learner-control is fraught with difficulties but it is mainly in relation to the former that the latter finds its expression.

According to O'Malley and Chamot, learning strategies are 'the special thoughts or behaviors that individuals use to help them comprehend, learn, or retain new information'[3]. 'Learning strategies are mental steps or operations that learners use to learn a new language and to regulate their efforts to do so'. To a greater or lesser degree, the strategies and learning styles that someone adopts 'may partly reflect personal preference rather than innate endowment'.

Language learning is not merely a cognitive task. Learners do not only reflect on their learning in terms of the language input to which they are exposed, or the optimal strategies they need in order to achieve the goals they set. Rather, the success of a learning activity is, to some extent, contingent upon learners' stance towards the world and the learning activity in particular, their sense of self, and their desire to learn. As Candy (1991: 295-296) says, 'the how and the what of learning are intimately interwoven—the overall approach a learner adopts will significantly influence the shape of his or her learning outcomes'. In other words, language learning—as well as learning, in general—has also an affective component. 'Meeting and interiorizing the grammar of a foreign language is not simply an intelligent, cognitive act. It is a highly affective one too—' define 'affective variables' as the 'emotionally relevant characteristics of the individual that influence how she/he will respond to any situation'. Other scholars, such as Shumann and Larsen-Freeman and Long attach less importance to learners' emotions, claiming that 'social and psychological factors' give a more suitable description for students' reactions to the learning process. Amongst the social and affective variables at work, self-esteem and desire to learn are deemed to be the most crucial factors 'in the learner's ability to overcome occasional setbacks or minor mistakes in the process of learning a second language'[4]. In this light, it is necessary to shed some light on learner attitudes and motivation. It is manifest that in language learning, people are motivated in different ways and to different degrees. Some learners like doing grammar and memorizing; others want to speak and role-play; others prefer reading and writing, while avoiding speaking. Furthermore, since '[the learning of a foreign language] involves an alteration in self-image, the adoption of new social and cultural behaviors and ways of being, and therefore has a significant impact on the social nature of the learner', an important distinction should be made between instrumental and integrative motivation.

To posit ways of fostering learner autonomy is certainly to posit ways of fostering teacher

autonomy, as teachers autonomy permeates into learners' autonomy. Nevertheless, our main focus will be on what the learner can do in order to attain a considerable degree of autonomy, even though the success of the learner is, to a great extent, determined—alas! vitiating—by the educational system and the requisite role of the teacher. A good way of collecting information on how students go about a learning task and helping them become aware of their own strategies is to assign a task and have them report what they are thinking while they are performing it. This self-report is called introspective, as learners are asked to introspect on their learning. In this case, 'the introspective self-report is a verbalization of one's stream of consciousness'[5]. Introspective reports are assumed to provide information on the strategies learners are using at the time of the report. However, this method suffers from one limitation: 'the concentration put on thinking aloud might detract from learners' ability to do the task efficiently', thus rendering the outcome of the report spurious and tentative. Another type of self-report is what has been dubbed as retrospective self-report, since learners are asked to think back or retrospect on their learning. Retrospective self-reports are quite open ended, in that there is no limit put on what students say in response to a question or statement that points to a topic in a general way. There are two kinds of retrospective self-reports: semistructured interviews and structured questionnaires. A semistructured interview may focus on a specific skill with a view to extracting information about learners' feelings towards particular skills (reading, listening, etc.), problems encountered, techniques resorted to in order to tackle these problems, and learners' views on optimal strategies or ways of acquiring specific skills or dealing with learning tasks. A structured questionnaire seeks the same information but in a different way: by dint of explicit questions and statements, and then asking learners to agree or disagree, write true or false, and so forth.

Littlewood makes a detailed explanation on how autonomy develops in a language learner through the process of language learning. He starts his explanation by distinguishing three kinds of autonomy to be developed relevant to language teaching as follows: Language teachers aim to develop students' ability to operate independently with the language and use the language to communicate in real, unpredictable situations. Language teachers aim to help their students to develop their ability to take responsibility for their own learning and to apply active, personally meaningful strategies to their work both inside and outside the classroom. Helping their students to increase their ability to communicate and learn independently, language teachers also try to reach the goal of helping their students to develop greater generalized autonomy as individuals. Then, in language teaching teachers need to help students develop motivation,

confidence, knowledge and skills that they require in order to communicate more independently, to learn more independently and to be more independent as individuals.

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